

Speculation on Similarities Between the Bohm Aharonov Effect and 1-D Reflection/Refraction

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In this note, we suggest that there is a close resemblance between the Bohm-Aharonov phase and a phase which may arise in 1-D reflection-refraction. We compare these two phenomena because in one scenario of the Bohm-Aharonov case one has a particle with constant momentum nevertheless interacting with a vector magnetic field which transforms like momentum under a Lorentz transformation. Thus, it is the phase accrued by both the particle and the A vector potential which represent the overall quantum phase. In the case of a particle or photon which refracts, we have argued in previous notes that $p_2 = n_2 p_1$ ($n_2 = \text{index of refraction in the second medium}$) is really an average because at some times the particle/photon interacts and at other times moves through a tiny vacuum space between molecules in n_2 . We argue that p_2 is really $p_1 + (p_2 - p_1)$, where $p_2 - p_1$ plays the role of A in the Bohm-Aharonov case. In other words, we imagine a particle photon which reaches an $n_1 - n_2$ junction (one dimension). The refracted beam may move a distance L in n_2 until it arrives at an $n_2 - n_3$ junction (with $n_3 > n_2 > n_1$) and reflects. It may then travel as $-p_2$ back to the $n_2 - n_1$ junction and refract out into n_1 again, but with a phase shift based on p_2 and L, i.e. $2p_2L + 3.14$. If $2L p_1$ is a multiple of 2π , then $(p_2 - p_1) 2L$ is the phase shift which mimics the Bohm-Aharonov one of $\int_0^x A(x') dx'$.

We also note that the treatment of a charged particle in an A field seems to arise from special relativity which we argue gives rise to free particle quantum mechanics. We show how the notion of a Lagrangian seems to arise from special relativity in this case.

Bohm-Aharonov Effect

In Newtonian mechanics, one focuses on the second law $dp/dt = \text{Force}$, which suggests that physicality is measured by forces and changes in momentum. In other words, if there is no change in momentum (magnitude, direction or both), then nothing has happened. Thus, it was a surprise when experiment confirmed Bohm and Aharonov's prediction that a charged particle moving in a vector magnetic potential field, A, which gives rise to a magnetic field and a magnetic field $B = \text{grad} \times A$ which does not change p (i.e. no force acting on p), could exhibit a phase shift effect due to A.

In particular, free particle quantum mechanics uses a wavefunction (complex probability for impulse delivery we argue) of:

$$\exp(i \int_0^x p dx) = \exp(ipx) \text{ for a } p = \text{constant} \quad ((1))$$

In the case of this non-force delivering B from A, one has:

$$\exp(ip(\text{particle})x + \int_0^x A(x')) \quad ((2))$$

In other words, there is an extra phase shift due to $A(x')$, the vector magnetic potential.

We note further that A Lorentz transforms like p and so in a sense there is a combined p of the particle with A leading to an overall p(total). It is this overall p which should also act like a quantum wavefunction because we have argued that free particle quantum mechanics arises from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant Action = -Et+px. A combined p of a particle with A (assuming they interact) would have this degeneracy $t=t_0+n\hbar/E$ and $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$ (n=integer), at least if it were constant. A(x'), however, is not constant, while p particle is (no force) so the overall p is not constant, but we argue that for each dx it maps to a constant p in this case. This approach however, cannot be used for bound quantum particle except in a semi-classical approximation. In a later section, we investigate this in more detail, but for now, we wish to suggest that there is a total p which exhibits quantum wavelength type effects and that A(x) being part of this contributes a phase as does p (particle).

The question we ask is: Does this effect appear in other scenarios in physics which are not normally associated with a Bohm-Aharonov effect? We argue that it appears in one dimensional reflection-refraction of a particle.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction Yielding a Bohm-Aharonov Phase

We consider the case of one-dimensional reflection-refraction for two index of refraction junctions: n_1-n_2 and n_2-n_3 separated by L with $n_3>n_2>n_1$.

Such a scenario may hold for a photon or for a particle with rest mass for which E remains the same, but each region has a different constant potential with a sharp change at each junction.

In such a case, one may have a refracted object with p_2 arise at the n_1-n_2 junction. It will move a distance L to the n_2-n_3 junction, creating a phase of p_2L . At the junction, it will reflect picking up a phase shift of 3.14 and then move with $-p_2$ a distance L so that the total phase is:

$$2p_2 L + 3.14 \quad ((3))$$

It may then refract out into n_1 and move with $-p_1$ but with the phase shift ((3)).

If L is not an integer multiple of $2*3.14/p_2$, then a phase appears ((3)) which will lead to interference with a reflected object at the n_1-n_2 junction which only has a phase of 3.14.

We suggest that this picture is really the same as the Bohm-Aharonov case with ((3)) being related to the Bohm-Aharonov phase through:

$$2 (p_2-p_1) L \quad ((4))$$

In other words, we suggest that p_2 (momentum) which describes the object in n_2 is really a combination of two momenta: one the particle momentum and the second, a momentum due to interactions with the molecules. In other words, a quantum object in n_2 sometimes interacts with molecules/atoms and at other times moves freely through a vacuum. Thus, p_2 is an average effect, much like the case of a total momentum of p (particle) and A(x) (vector magnetic potential) in the Bohm-Aharonov situation.

As a result, we suggest that an effect analogous to the Bohm-Aharonov phase exists in the above 1-D reflection-refraction situation.

Special Relativity and the Lagrangian

In the literature, the Bohm-Aharonov effect seems to be linked to classical Lagrangian theory. In particular, Lagrangian theory states that:

$$dL/dv \text{ partial} = p \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } L(v,x,t)$$

The Lagrangian must give rise to Newton's second law (considered here nonrelativistically).

((1)) shows that for a charged particle interacting with a magnetic field one has:

$$L = .5mv^2 + q/c \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{A} + q \phi \quad ((6))$$

Here we set $q \phi = 0$ (electrostatic potential) and consider one dimension, so $\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{A} = vA$. One may see from ((6)) that:

$$P(\text{total}) = mv + q/c A \quad ((7))$$

In other words, the overall $p(\text{total})$ consists of the nonrelativistic mv of the particle and $q/c A$ from the vector magnetic potential.

As shown in ((1)) the Hamiltonian $H = p(\text{total})v - L$ is:

$$H = 1/2m (p - q/cA)^2 \quad ((8)) \quad p = p(\text{total}) \text{ here}$$

In quantum mechanics, p is then replaced with $-d/dx$ and not the momentum of the charged particle. This suggests a wavefunction of::

$$\exp(i \int_{(0-x)}^{(x)} (p - q/cA) dx') \quad ((9))$$

So that $-i \text{grad}$ yields the overall momentum and not just that of the charged particle.

Thus, a charged particle will have a constant $p(\text{particle})$ and a phase $\int p(\text{particle}) dx = p(\text{particle})x$ while the magnetic vector potential yields a phase of:

$$\int_{(0,x)} dx' A(x') \quad ((10))$$

((10)) is an extra phase shift which may lead to interference with a particle with $p(\text{particle})$ which does not pass through an x interval containing $A(x)$.

We suggest that one may obtain these results directly from special relativity, which we also argue gives rise to free particle quantum mechanics in the first place. In particular, if one has a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$, at t (with no A) and views it from a frame moving with constant $-v$, then one has the Lorentz invariant (which we call Action here)

$$\text{Action} = -Et + px \quad ((11))$$

Action is degenerate for $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$ and $t=t_0+n\hbar/E$ ($n=\text{integer}$) so there are intervals in t and x defined through E and p . If one seeks a probability which respects these intervals, but leads to $P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$ (and a similar expression for E), then one has $\exp(ipx)$.

Next, we consider the case of a charged rest mass, m_0 , at $x=0$ at t with an $A_1(x)$, magnetic potential, which causes no force on m_0 . A_1 transforms as a momentum and the electrostatic potential is 0 so as seen from a frame moving with $-v$ (constant) one has:

m_{occ} , A_1 transform to:

$$E' = \gamma v A_1 + \gamma m_0 \quad \text{and} \quad p' = \gamma m_0 v + \gamma A_1 \quad ((12))$$

If one calls $\gamma A_1 = A$ in a frame in which the particle moves with v and uses the nonrelativistic approximation for the particle, then the Lorentz invariant is:

$$\text{Action} = -Et + px \quad (\text{here we drop the primes but } E, x, p \text{ really all have primes})$$

$E_{\text{particle}} = m_{\text{occ}}$, but we ignore this a nonrelativistic scenario so only vA remains. Thus:

$$\text{Action} = -vAt + p(\text{particle})x + Ax \quad ((13))$$

If one considers a dx for which everything is constant and calls $\text{Action} = Lt$ and $v=x/t$ mapping to this dx region and its values, then:

$$L = -vA + p(\text{particle})v + Av = -vA + v(p_{\text{total}}) \quad ((14))$$

((14)), however, is the result from classical theory which does not use special relativity.

We note that quantum mechanics seems to arise from special relativity and this theory should apply to $p(\text{total})$ so both $p(\text{particle})$ and q/cA contribute to the quantum phase, i.e.

$$\exp(i(p_{\text{total}} - q/cA)x) = \exp(i(p(\text{particle}) + q/cA) dx') \quad \text{where } x' \text{ runs from } (0, x) \text{ etc} \quad ((15))$$

In other words, to obtain a Bohm-Aharonov effect, one need only apply quantum mechanical rules which follow from special relativity to $p(\text{total})$ because $p(\text{total})$ transforms under a Lorentz transformation and describes the overall $p(\text{particle})$ interacting with A .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Bohm-Aharonov phase is very similar to a phase which arises if a particle first refracts at an n_1 - n_2 junction, then reflects at an n_2 - n_3 junction, L away, returns to the n_2 - n_1 junctions and refracts back into n_1 . We suggest that while the particle has p_2 , this is only an average. It is a combination of the original p_1 in n_1 with an extra average p_2 - p_1 due to interactions with molecules/atoms. Thus, this is an almost identical scenario to a charged particle interacting with a vector magnetic potential A , if one considers p_1 to remain in n_2 with the extra p_2 - p_1 being assigned to a kind of average field.

We also argue that the Bohm-Aharonov scheme may be shown to arise from special relativity instead of using the usual classical theory of a charged particle moving in a magnetic field.

References

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